

HIT/MISS PROBABILITY OF DETECTION FOR ARTIFICIAL DEFECTS IN DISCONTINUOUS LONG FIBER COMPOSITES VIA TRANSIENT INFRARED THERMOGRAPHY

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ABSTRACT

The inspection of discontinuous long fibre-reinforced plastic composites (DLFRPCs) presents significant challenges due to the stochastic nature of their meso-structure, particularly in detecting subsurface defects that may compromise performance in critical applications. Traditional non-destructive testing (NDT) methods struggle with the variability introduced by randomly oriented fibre strands, necessitating more advanced techniques to ensure reliable detection across varying defect depths and sizes. This study investigates the use of transient infrared thermography (T-IRT), employing halogen lamp heating, to detect subsurface voids and inclusions in DLFRPCs. T-IRT offers rapid full-field inspection and the ability to highlight thermal gradients associated with defects, making it well-suited for heterogeneous materials. Compression-molded plates (5×5 inches, 2.5 mm thick) composed of 0.25×2-inch unidirectional prepreg platelets were used. The orientation and placement of individual platelets resulted in non-uniform thermal responses, complicating defect detection and precluding the definition of a representative “sound” region. To address this, artificial defects in the form of flat-bottom holes (FBHs) were introduced at controlled depths and diameters. A pre/post scan approach was developed to calculate corrected thermal contrast at each FBH location, isolating defect-related signals from background variability. Defect detection was defined by a contrast threshold, and binary outcomes were analyzed using logistic regression within a hit/miss Probability of Detection (POD) framework. POD curves were generated to evaluate the influence of defect size on detectability. The results show that increasing defect diameter correlates with higher detection probability, as expected. However, the transition in detection is more gradual than in typical CFRP inspections, and confidence bounds are broader, attributed to the stochastic mesostructure of the DLFRPCs and associated signal variability. The pre/post scan method enabled robust contrast evaluation without relying on reference sound areas, a key contribution for defect quantification in complex materials. The findings demonstrate the feasibility of T-IRT combined with statistical POD for characterizing subsurface damage in DLFRPCs. This approach provides a foundation for optimizing inspection protocols and supports broader application of thermography in automotive and aerospace composite evaluation.

1 INTRODUCTION

Non-Destructive Testing (NDT) techniques are important for quality assurance and structural health monitoring in advanced composite materials [1]. Among these, Infrared Thermography (IRT) offers significant advantages due to its rapid, contactless inspection capability, particularly for identifying subsurface anomalies [2]. When applied in a transient mode, Transient Infrared Thermography (T-IRT), the method captures thermal diffusion responses following controlled heating, enabling the detection of internal features such as voids, delaminations, or inclusions. Discontinuous Long Fibre Reinforced Composites (DLFRPCs), such as platelet-molded carbon fibre systems, present unique challenges for NDT. Their highly stochastic mesostructure, characterized by randomly distributed and oriented fibre bundles, leads to significant variability in thermal behavior. This complicates defect detection and reduces the reliability of traditional contrast-based evaluation methods that rely on reference regions with uniform properties. To address these challenges, there is a need to quantify the detection performance of T-IRT in LDFCs using robust statistical frameworks. Probability of Detection (POD) analysis is the standard method to quantify the reliability of NDT techniques. Two common approaches exist: the continuous response method, (\hat{a} vs. a) [3], and the binary classification method, hit/miss [4], which is used for this work.

This work presents a comprehensive POD analysis for simulated defects in compression-molded long discontinuous fibre composites inspected via T-IRT. A rigorous methodology is adopted, including the manufacturing of defect-free plates, precise machining of flat-bottom holes (FBHs) as artificial defects, execution of front-side transient thermography using halogen lamp excitation, and advanced signal processing through Thermal Signal Reconstruction (TSR) and a custom signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) classification approach. Detection reliability is quantified using a hit/miss POD framework, where a binary classification threshold is applied to matched pre- and post-drilling thermographic responses. Statistical confidence bounds are established using a logistic regression model and the delta method. The results provide new insights into the capabilities and limitations of T-IRT for inspecting LDFCs and offer practical guidance for improving defect detectability in materials with inherently random mesostructure.

2 MATERIAL SYSTEM AND PLATE MANUFACTURING

The composite plates used in this study were manufactured from XForge™ VZ TDS, a long discontinuous carbon fiber reinforced epoxy prepreg supplied by DowAksa. This material is designed for isothermal compression molding at 150°C with rapid cure cycles under 3 minutes for parts under 9.5 mm thickness. The randomly distributed platelets give rise to a highly stochastic meso-structure. Plate fabrication was carried out at Old Dominion University (ODU) under controlled conditions (see Fig. 1a). Each plate was initially molded within a 5 × 5-inch (127 × 127 mm) aluminum tool (see Fig. 1b). After curing, the plates were trimmed to final dimensions of 4 × 4 inches (101.6 × 101.6 mm) to remove edge effects and ensure dimensional uniformity. The nominal thickness of all plates was 2.5 mm, with an actual measured mean of 2.579 mm and a standard deviation $s = 0.119$ mm. These results confirm good geometric consistency, which is important for reliable thermographic and statistical analysis, especially considering the mold charging process is non-trivial due to the semi-preg format of the material, which requires careful manual placement. Once an optimized process was established, all subsequent plates were subjected to both IRT and UTPA prior to further processing. Only plates confirmed to be free of internal defects via UTPA were retained for testing. A total of eleven defect-free plates were selected based on these criteria. Following inspection, artificial defects were introduced in the form of Flat-Bottom Holes (FBHs), precisely machined into the back surface of each plate. These FBHs serve as controlled defect simulants with known geometries, enabling the quantification of detection capability through thermographic contrast analysis.

Figure 1. a) Detail of the material after cutting b) Material placed in the 5x5 in mold.

3 DEFECT SIMULATION USING FLAT BOTTOM HOLES (FBHS)

In POD studies, artificial defects are introduced to replicate damage modes such as delaminations or voids commonly observed in impacted or poorly consolidated composites [5]. In this work, artificial defects were implemented using Flat-Bottom Holes, selected over other options such as Teflon inserts. While Teflon inserts are often used to simulate delaminations in traditional composite laminates, they proved unsuitable for DLFRCs manufactured via hot press compression molding. During pressing, inserts tend to shift from their intended positions due to resin and fiber flow and are distorted as they become entangled within the disordered fiber bundles. This results in unpredictable geometries and locations, conditions that are incompatible with quantitative and repeatable defect detection studies.

Figure 2. Flat bottom hole (FBH) index versus aspect ratio for the 55 simulated defects used in this study. This image show comparison between measured and nominal values.

In contrast, FBHs can be machined post-curing using precision CNC milling, allowing tight control over defect diameter, depth, and location. This ensures high geometric accuracy and repeatability across samples, making FBHs a reliable and reproducible defect type for thermographic POD evaluation. Due to machining tolerances inherent to the milling process, small variations in FBH depth were expected and confirmed. The

shallowest FBH in each plate (closest to the inspection surface) was designed to maintain a minimum remaining wall thickness of 0.5 mm to prevent breakthrough. Considering potential depth errors of up to ± 0.3 mm from the milling setup, this safety margin was necessary. The actual measured depths of these shallowest FBHs ranged from 0.15 mm to 0.45 mm, with a mean value of 0.348 mm and a standard deviation of 0.104 mm. A total of 55 FBHs (Fig. 2) were distributed across 11 plates, consistent with the minimum recommendations outlined in MIL-HDBK-1823A and ASTM E2862. The FBH diameters range from 2 mm to 22 mm, in 2 mm increments, with five depth levels per plate. Each plate contains a unique diameter and five FBHs positioned at nominal depths of 0.5 mm, 0.8 mm, 1.1 mm, 1.5 mm, and 1.9 mm from the front (inspection) surface. This configuration covers a realistic range of subsurface defect scenarios, from easily detectable shallow defects to more challenging deeper ones that may be partially masked by backwall reflections. FBHs were drilled under constant feed and speed conditions using a precision CNC machine to minimize heat-affected zones (see Fig. 3). All dimensions were subsequently verified using a caliper. For example, Plate 001 contains FBHs ranging from 0.15 mm to 0.69 mm in depth, while Plate 011 includes defects from 0.35 mm to 1.82 mm, paired with a 22 mm diameter. Overall, the controlled and fully characterized FBH dataset developed in this study provides a rigorous foundation for assessing the detection performance of the T-IRT system and for quantifying POD in relation to defect geometry and depth.

Figure 3. Flat Bottom Hole plate design. Top: geometric design. Bottom: images of the manufacturing process (left) and the final fabricated plate (right).

4 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP FOR TRANSIENT INFRARED THERMOGRAPHY

Each plate was inspected using a Transient Infrared Thermography setup configured for front-side heating and observation. The DLFRPC material under investigation, presents unique challenges for thermographic evaluation. First, there is limited prior literature on applying IRT to such materials, and second, their inherent local fibre orientation variability introduces significant spatial non-uniformity in thermal behaviour. This makes conventional approaches in POD, where the thermal response over a defect is compared with a neighbouring sound area, unsuitable. Due to the randomness of the fibre orientation distribution (FOD), "sound" zones [6] may exhibit vastly different transient responses depending on local conductivity and heat flow patterns. This limitation is illustrated in Figure 4, which shows two distinct regions on the same plate with different thermal decay curves despite both being defect-free.

To overcome this, a differential inspection approach was implemented. Each plate was scanned twice using T-IRT: once immediately after trimming (baseline condition), and once after FBH drilling. During both

scans, all boundary and measurement conditions were kept constant, including ambient temperature, lamp intensity and position, camera distance, and sample alignment. To further minimize experimental error, four defect-free reference areas on each plate were used to calculate the average first temporal derivative of the thermal signal before and after FBH drilling. This allowed for minor residual normalization and correction, ensuring that contrast changes were attributable to the presence of the artificial defects rather than material variability or setup drift. The final evaluation of detectability was based on the ratio of thermal responses between the same area *before* and *after* - FBH drilling. This comparative metric captures local thermal contrast due to the artificial defect while compensating for the spatial variability inherent in the DLFRCs.

Figure 4. Left: Analyzed pixel locations. Right: Temperature profile of the analyzed pixels.

To enable reproducible and precise alignment between pre- and post-defect scans, a customized 3D-printed fixture was developed to hold the infrared (IR) camera, halogen lamps, and specimen in fixed relative positions (Fig. 5). The fixture allows the specimen to be inserted and removed while preserving a fixed geometry between all components. The plate is held in position on a height-calibrated platform to ensure repeatable distance and centering relative to the optical axis of the camera and illumination sources. The inspection was conducted in Dr. Kravchenko's laboratory at the University of British Columbia using a C-CheckIR system developed by Automation Technology (see Fig. 5). The setup included an IRS x640 NDT uncooled infrared camera equipped with a 12 mm wide lens, providing a thermal sensitivity of 75 mK and a spatial resolution of 640×480 pixels. For heating, two 850 W dimmable halogen lamps were used, controlled by an IRX-Box, which synchronized the entire system, including the IR-NDT Transient & Pulse Software Evaluation Module. One of the challenges in T-IRT is interpreting noisy thermal data. To create the final thermal image and improve signal-to-noise ratio and extract meaningful features such as contrast and defect depth, Thermal Signal Reconstruction (TSR) was used. This method computes temperature derivatives with respect to time and was implemented using custom MATLAB scripts based on [7,8].

Figure 5. IRT setup

5 STATISTICAL POD ANALYSIS

In POD analysis, two main approaches are typically used: a continuous model based on response data (â vs. a), and a binary hit/miss model [5,9]. Both aim to quantify the likelihood of detecting a defect as a function of size or other damage parameters. The response-based method assumes normally distributed variability in measured signals and derives the POD curve using a cumulative distribution function above a decision threshold. Detailed derivations and assumptions are available in the referenced standards and literature [10]. In this study, the hit/miss approach was selected due to the variability in thermal signal response caused by the stochastic nature of the composite material. A defect was classified as detected when the corrected local thermal contrast exceeded a defined threshold. The resulting binary outcomes were analyzed using logistic regression, and confidence bounds were computed using the delta method. This section describes the model selection, parameter estimation, and interpretation of results based on this approach.

5.1 Hit/Miss model selection

The hit/miss analysis is a statistical method used when the inspection output is binary, meaning the result for each flaw is either a hit (detected) or a miss (not detected). This approach is especially relevant when the NDT system provides a yes/no decision instead of a continuous signal.

Ordinary linear models assume continuous and unbounded outcomes, with normally distributed residuals. However, hit/miss data are discrete and bounded between 0 and 1. For such data, the residuals follow a binomial distribution, making ordinary least squares inappropriate. Generalized Linear Models (GLMs) resolve this by using a suitable link function to transform the binary outcome into a form compatible with linear modeling.

In hit/miss analysis, a flaw is classified as detected if the signal exceeds the threshold; otherwise, it is missed. This approach is particularly robust when response measurements are not reliably quantifiable, which may occur in materials such as DLFRCs with complex, stochastic microstructures.

Several link functions are available to model PoD as a function of flaw size a :

Logit (log-odds)
$$POD(a) = \frac{1}{1 + \exp(-Xf)} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Probit (log-normal)} \quad \text{POD}(a) = \Phi(Xf) \quad (2)$$

$$\begin{array}{ll} \text{Complementary} & \text{log-log} \\ \text{(cloglog)} & \end{array} \quad \text{POD}(a) = 1 - \exp(-\exp(Xf)) \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Log-log} \quad \text{POD}(a) = \exp(-\exp(-Xf)) \quad (4)$$

Where $Xf = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot \ln(a)$ is a linear function of the explanatory variable. $\Phi(\cdot)$ denotes the standard cumulative distribution function.

The choice of link function impacts the shape of the PoD curve and the estimated $a_{90/95}$. Symmetric links (logit and probit) are preferred for symmetric data, while skewed data may be better modeled with cloglog (left-skewed) or log-log (right-skewed) links. In practice, logit and probit yield similar results for well-behaved data.

To estimate the parameters of the POD model, Maximum Likelihood Estimation (MLE) was used to fit a logistic regression to the binary hit/miss data. The model relates the probability of detection to flaw size, and the log-likelihood function was optimized to determine the intercept and slope. A key performance metric is $a_{90/95}$, defined as the smallest flaw size detectable with 90% probability at 95% confidence. Confidence intervals were computed using the delta method, which propagates uncertainty from the fitted model parameters to the POD curve through partial derivatives and the variance–covariance matrix. The $a_{90/95}$ was obtained by solving for the lower 95% bound of the POD curve at 90% probability. This approach follows the procedure outlined in the ASM Handbook [10] and remains widely adopted for its efficiency and robustness. Alternative methods such as Bayesian inference or bootstrapping may be used in cases with limited data or non-ideal model assumptions.

5.2 Defect Classification and POD Curve Interpretation

To select an appropriate detection threshold ϕ_{dec} and classify defects for hit/miss POD analysis, a custom signal-to-noise ratio approach was developed. This method compares thermal contrast at the same physical location before and after FBH insertion. The objective is to isolate the defect-related signal while minimizing the impact of stochastic background variation and environmental factors (e.g., ambient temperature, lamp distance, humidity).

The local thermal contrast change at the defect site is computed as:

$$\Delta\phi = \phi_{post} - \phi_{pre}$$

where ϕ_{post} and ϕ_{pre} represent thermal contrast in the same region of interest (ROI) in the post- and pre-drilling scans, respectively. To compensate for global changes in experimental conditions, the average contrast change in unaffected reference regions $\Delta\phi_{ref}$ is subtracted:

$$\Delta\phi_{corrected} = \Delta\phi - \Delta\phi_{ref}$$

A defect is marked as detected if the corrected contrast change exceeds the detection threshold:

$$\Delta\phi_{corrected} \geq \phi_{dec}$$

A threshold $\phi_{dec} = 1.2$ was selected based on values commonly used in thermographic NDT studies (typically ranging from 1.2 to 1.5 for TSR and phase-based metrics [5,11]) and was empirically validated to balance sensitivity and false positive rate.

This approach enables robust defect classification without relying on assumptions of spatial uniformity or Gaussian noise distribution. It is particularly suitable for composites like DLF RPC, where random fiber

orientation and local mesostructure variation can compromise traditional referencing methods. By leveraging spatially aligned pre/post scan data, this method provides a consistent basis for classification under realistic noise conditions.

5.3 POD Analysis and Results

The resulting POD curve from the hit/miss classification is shown in Figure 6. The model demonstrates the expected increase in detection probability with increasing FBH size. However, the curve exhibits a relatively shallow slope and wide confidence bound, indicating variability in thermal contrast response for defects of similar size. This behaviour is attributed to the stochastic mesostructure of DLFRCs, where local fibre orientation, platelet overlap, and resin-rich zones lead to non-uniform heat flow. These effects introduce background fluctuations that degrade defect signal repeatability and widen the statistical uncertainty of detection.

The estimated 90% detection threshold (a_{90}) was reached at an FBH ratio of approximately 22, indicating that defects of this size were detected with high probability under the current inspection conditions. However, the 90% detection at 95% statistical confidence ($a_{90/95}$) was not achieved within the tested flaw size range. This outcome highlights a key limitation in applying classical POD assumptions to random-fiber composites: material heterogeneity imposes a fundamental constraint on statistical detectability. This limitation arises not from deficiencies in the inspection method, but from inherent variability in the composite's mesostructure.

Figure 6. POD curve from the hit/miss classification.

Despite these challenges, the study demonstrates that robust thermographic POD analysis is feasible when adapted methodologies are employed. The pre/post scan approach with SNR-based classification provides a reliable framework for inspection in non-uniform composites.

6 CONCLUSIONS

A DLFRPC specimen containing 55 Flat Bottom Holes distributed across 11 plates was inspected using Transient Infrared Thermography. To address the lack of thermally uniform regions, a common limitation in randomly structured composites, a pre/post scan methodology was implemented. This approach enabled isolation of defect signals through differential thermal contrast, making it suitable for materials with significant background variability. Defect classification was performed using a custom signal-to-noise metric and hit/miss POD analysis was conducted using a detection threshold of 1.2.

The resulting POD curve exhibited a gradual increase in detection probability with flaw size, as expected. The 90% detection threshold (a_{90}) was reached at an estimated FBH aspect ratio of 22. However, the 90% detection at 95% statistical confidence ($a_{90/95}$) was not achieved within the tested range. This result highlights a key limitation when applying conventional POD models to composites with random internal architecture. In such materials, the assumption of consistent defect detectability breaks down due to the influence of local mesostructure, not shortcomings in the inspection technique itself.

"The relatively shallow slope and wide confidence intervals of the POD curve reflect the stochastic variability in thermal response caused by factors such as random fibre orientation, platelet misalignment, and non-uniform resin distribution. These features affect heat diffusion paths and result in inconsistent thermal contrast at defect sites, differing from those observed in CFRP studies [5,9,10,12].

Despite these challenges, the study demonstrates that reliable thermographic POD assessment is achievable for DLFRPCs when adapted analysis strategies are used. The integration of spatially aligned pre/post scans and contrast-based SNR metrics offers a robust framework for flaw classification in the presence of complex background noise. These findings establish a basis for developing standardized inspection protocols in stochastic composite materials.

Future improvements may include multimodal inspection strategies, such as combining thermography with ultrasonic or X-ray methods, to reduce uncertainty and improve detection confidence.

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